

Fig. 1. Time versus per cent yield during Post-polymerization of Methylmethacrylate by Sugar/HCl as supporting electrolyte.

[HCl]=0.72M, [Sugar]=0.3M [MMA]=1%(v/v)
Current=100 mA × 60 mins. temp.=32.5°.

sugar concentration of about 0.1 to 0.3 is just about the optimum and the minimum acid concentration necessary to produce a high yield is about 0.72 M. The post-polymerization is rather fast during the first few hours as is shown for a typical system in Fig. 1. The $[\eta]$ -value however does not change much with progress of post-polymerization—a characteristic which is typical of post-polymerization.

Though aqueous redox polymerization is strongly inhibited by traces of dissolved oxygen, post-polymerization is not so sensitive to air, no special precaution being therefore necessary to exclude air in the latter case. So the reported post-polymerization does not involve redox polymerization. However, this is a free radical process as is shown by strong inhibition by hydroquinone. HCl has possibly a dual function, serving as the electrolyte as well as producer of the right pH. The sugar gets oxidised at the anode possibly producing the initiating free radical. It is likely that each monomer swollen oligomeric free radical formed by electro initiation constitutes the isolated loci where post-polymerization takes place. The gelation appears to be due to the presence of sugar. It is likely that some kind of crosslinked polymer is formed due to multiple free radical formation (by oxidation or chain transfer) on the same sugar molecule.

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A Peculiar Current-Increasing Effect of Cellophane Membranes.

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IN course of our work on non-Faradaic electrolysis^{1,2} we made the surprising observation that on interposing a cellophane membrane between the two electrodes, with the purpose of checking inter-electrode diffusion and convective or mechanical mixing, the current showed an increase (+ Δi) instead of the expected decrease.

This can be easily observed with an experimental set-up as shown in Fig. 1 using water as the electrolyte.

Fig. 1. Experimental set-up for studying the Current Increasing ($+\Delta i$) effect of Cellophane Membrane (T=Glass or Plastic tube; M=Cellophane Membrane;

A=Ammeter (milli or micro as necessary);
B=Bank of Lead Accumulators or D. C. Power Supply).

When a constant D. C. voltage is applied between the two electrodes (without the interposed cellophane membrane as shown by the dotted line) the current slowly increases with time and tends to attain a more or less steady value (Fig. 2, Curve 1). If the same experiment is repeated under exactly the same condition except that the cathode (i.e. mouth of tube T) is covered by a cellophane membrane shown by the dotted line, a large increase of current is observed instead of an expected decrease; there is a large instantaneous increase and an enormous (nearly five times) eventual increase of current (Fig. 2, Curve 2). Using a plastic tube instead of the glass tube or using a cellophane sac to enclose the cathode gives the same kind of result. Instead of a cellophane membrane a good filter paper (Whatman No. 4) shows similar albeit much less $+\Delta i$ effect. If the anode is enclosed instead of the cathode, the $+\Delta i$ effect is very much less (compare curve 3 and 4). This $+\Delta i$ -effect tends to vanish with increasing concentration of dissolved electrolyte.

At first we thought this to be due to the leaching out of some ionic impurity present in cellophane. However, this did not seem possible for various reasons.

Fig. 2. Typical curves showing change of current on interposing cellophane membrane (Time variation also shown) ($V=200$ Volts).

1. Cathode inside T but without cellophane.
2. Same as 1 but with cellophane membrane (M).
3. Anode inside T but without cellophane.
4. Same as 3 but with cellophane membrane (M).

Firstly, the cellophane used was pre-treated for days with repeated charges of hot conductivity water and the leach water did not show any ionic leaching by conductivity measurements. Secondly, by a suitable device the membrane could be removed from its position and again put in its place repeatedly and everytime a 'kick' in the microammeter needle could be observed. As a matter of fact if the tube T is dispensed with and a cellophane membrane is immersed near the cathode more or less covering the latter, a 'kick', though very small, of the microammeter needle is observed. It appears that cellophane by mere contact with water somehow increases its conductivity.

Since the 'leaching-out' idea falls through, we thought about the possibility of some electrolyte being formed near the enclosed electrode (viz. the cathode). This idea however fails to explain at least the initial almost instantaneous increase and also the transient nature of the increase; besides the final increase appears to be too much for such an explanation. Also, it is difficult to see why the $+\Delta i$ -effect is much stronger with cathode than with anode enclosed. But a crucial blow to such a theory is given by the fact that even very low A.C also shows this $+\Delta i$ -effect (see later).

It appears that for an explanation we have to look for a different mechanism of current conduction than the conventional one. Since this $+\Delta i$ -effect is stronger

with dilute solution and low current, and since we have demonstrated that many anomalous features accompany electrolysis under this condition (called non-Faradaic electrolysis¹⁻³), it is likely that the explanation in these two cases may have something in common. Since hydrated electron formation near the cathode has been one of the suggested explanations of non-Faradaic electrolysis we may assume that a steady state concentration of hydrated electrons builds up inside the cathode chamber, which leak out leading to the enhancement of current. This is theoretically possible because electrons are being pumped in at the rate of about 10^{15} electrons/sec at about 1 mA whereas the hydrated electrons get annihilated at a rate constant of the order of 10^9 - 10^{11} per sec. So the cathode chamber after some time becomes a veritable storehouse of electrons which leak out at a much faster rate than the migration speed of ions. So electronic conduction takes place along with ionic conduction and is responsible for the $+\Delta i$ -effect. This build-up of electrons near the cathode which is almost instantaneous is responsible for the observed reduction of dissolved nitrogen to ammonia in a similar apparatus as reported by Palit⁴.

Any way, it appears that some kind of extra 'pumping' action of charged carriers under the action of an electric field comes into play on interposition of a cellophane membrane particularly near the cathode.

Since a good portion of the $+\Delta i$ is instantaneous it is expected that A.C. would also show this $+\Delta i$ -effect. We have found this to be true with two kinds of experiments. Firstly, by using mains A.C. we have found that by simple immersion of a cellophane membrane between two electrodes, with water as the electrolyte, there is an upward 'kick' of the microammeter and on subsequent removal of the cellophane a downward 'kick'; and this could be repeated any number of times. Secondly, the measured conductivity of water with a conventional A.C. bridge increases by nearly a factor of two when a cellophane membrane is dipped inside the conductivity cell between the two electrodes; furthermore this change is found to be reversible. It is evident that the current conduction mechanism through water or a poorly conducting solution changes considerably in the presence of a cellophane membrane in a way which is rather difficult to understand.

References

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Some Observations on the Electronic Spectra of Terpyridyl Copper Chloride.

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THE commonest structure of the pentacoordinated complexes of metals is a trigonal bipyramid (D_{3h}) although a few square pyramidal structures are known. The most well-known example of a trigonal bipyramidal complex of copper is monoterpyridyl copper chloride. Although the earlier¹ x-ray data suggested that zinc terpyridyl complex is a distorted trigonal bipyramid, with which the copper complex is isomorphous, the latter work² indicates the structure to be square pyramid. Each unit cell contains two complex molecules, the chlorine atom of the second molecule coordinates (called hydrogen bonded) with the copper atom of the first giving an effectively bridged structure. In the latter case we have effectively hexacoordinated complexes with three N and three Cl atoms surrounding the copper atom commonest symmetry of such a structure will be D_3 . X-ray study by Goldschmid and Stephenson³ shows Zn (terpy) Cl_2 to have 62% trigonal bipyramidal character. Einstein and Penfold⁴ have shown Zn (terpy) Cl_2 has five coordinated trigonal bipyramidal structure.

An ideal trigonal bipyramidal structure has the symmetry D_{3h} and from the d orbital energy level scheme⁵ for a d^9 atom such as copper (a system with one hole) two transitions are expected, viz ${}^2E' \leftarrow {}^2A_1'$ and ${}^2E'' \leftarrow {}^2A_1'$, the latter is electronically forbidden. If instead we regard the complex to be trigonal (D_3), then we expect the following transitions ${}^1A_1 \leftarrow {}^2E$ (xy polarised) and ${}^2E \leftarrow {}^2E$. The latter will split into two transitions of species A and E one being Z and the other xy polarised.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of powdered crystals of [Zn (Terpy)] Cl_2 (—) and powdered crystals of [Zn (terpy)] Cl_2 , [Cu(terpy)] Cl_2 (-----)